

NATURAL COARSE AGGREGATE MODIFIED BY WASTE STEEL SLAG AND ITS APPLICATION IN THE SUBBASE OF HIGHWAY IN OMAN

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Abstract

The world is moving towards sustainability to conserve natural resources. Many environmentally harmful materials produced by different industries that cannot be recycled can be exploited as a substitute for natural resources. The presence of steel slag in millions of tons around the world has become a negative impact on the environment. In the effects of climate change, there is a need to move towards sustainability. The use of steel slag which is produced by the steel factories located in the country will reduce the depletion of natural resources, at the same time, a place can be found to dispose of them and reduce environmental damage and burial costs. The main objective of this research is to specify the optimum mix of natural coarse aggregate and coarse steel slag in the subbase layer. California Bearing Ratio and Aggregate Impact Value experiments are the main parameters that will be used to evaluate each mix. As a result, it turns out that the use of 19% of steel slag will meet the required efficiency for the paving subbase layer.

Keywords: Flexible Pavement; Sustainable Pavements; Subbase; Steel Slag

1. INTRODUCTION

New roads and diverse paths have become one of the most important reasons for the development of countries, so developed countries seek to establish modern roads of high quality and efficiency, but at the same time, they aim to reduce construction costs and decrease the depletion of natural resources [1]. Therefore, they seek to find an alternative to natural resources by recycling materials or using materials that are present in large quantities with the inability to recycle them [2]. The types of pavements are classified into flexible pavement, which is the most common in the world, especially in Oman, and rigid pavement, which is used in ports and places with high loads [3]. The pavement consists of four main layers which are surface, base, subbase, and subgrade [4]. The surface layer's primary function is to support the tire's high pressure and to keep the pavement's structure dry [5]. Granular substances including crushed stone, crushed and uncrushed

gravel, and sand are used to create the base layer. It is mostly stabilized with Portland cement and asphalt. Just above the subgrade layer is the subbase layer. Also, it is built with high-quality materials like those used to build subgrade layers.

Subbase is a crucial layer of flexible pavement that serves as a foundation for the building of a road base, a secondary load distribution layer, and a drainage layer [6]. A sub-base layer's rigidity is significant because it strengthens the flexible pavement [7]. These characteristics guarantee that the materials meet a certain standard of quality [8]. With the following primary qualities: suitable strength, stiffness, water permeability, long-term volumetric stability, and chemical stability for pavements of durable rolling resistance, offering good road-holding conditions and simple transit [9]. There are many soils that cannot be used in the subbase layer due to their weakness so by adding some material to them the bearing capacity will increase and the waste material can be exploited [10]. Those materials are economical and have the required strength that the subbase is needed. The type of furnace, the grade of steel, and the pretreatment technique all affect the chemical composition of steel slag [11]. The minerals olivine, merwinite, free-CaO, tetra-calcium aluminoferrite (C4AF), tricalcium silicate (C3S), olivine, merwinite, and RO phase are all found in steel slag [12]. The manner in that steel slag is used is directly tied to its chemical and physical properties. Steel slag can be processed to produce high-quality aggregates that are comparable to those found in natural aggregates because of their great strength and durability [13]. Steel slag is a suitable building material for hydraulic engineering projects due to its high bulk density, high level of strength and abrasion, and rough texture [14].

The purpose of the subbase is to strengthen the street against sudden shocks, and at the same time, the cost must be taken into consideration [15]. The objective is to use as few cost-effective materials as possible to achieve the appropriate curb thickness. The mixture of steel slag and limestone has a higher resistance to deflection and vertical strain in the subbase layer and this blend mix increases the mechanical properties like resilient modulus, maximum dry density, and California bearing ratio of subbase materials which will decrease the thickness of subbase [16]. Steel slag can now be used as subbase materials on a big scale because of advancements in steel slag treating and processing technology over the past few decades. Nonetheless, the usage of steel slag aggregates in buildings, particularly as a granular material, has not been very widespread [17]. By using steel slag instead of natural rocks for construction, we can save our natural rock supplies and lessen the demand for dumping sites [18]. Modified expansive soil shows a suppressed plasticity index and enhanced CBR and UCS with the increase in optimum adjusted and activated steel slag (AASS) content and curing period. The performance of the compacted soils with 5%–7% AASS content satisfies the requirements for subbase according to Chinese standards [19]. Research has shown the possibility of using these materials in road infrastructures to promote the objectives set out by the sustainable development goals to promote the circular economy and sustainable construction [20].

As a part of infrastructure development, the building of new roads and the upgrading of old highways are booming nowadays [21]. One of the most popular techniques for determining the strength of a subgrade soil, subbase, and base course material for the

design of pavement thickness for roads is the California Bearing Ratio test. The California bearing ratio test is a penetration test used to measure the sub-base tensile strength of pavements and roadways [22]. In pavement design, the California Bearing Ratio (CBR) is the parameter that is nearly always employed to describe soils. Several attempts have been made to connect CBR to soil characteristics to avoid laboratory testing. However, the time and money required for the laboratory tests to determine CBR [23]. The laborious and drawn-out laboratory California Bearing Ratio (CBR) test is used to evaluate the soil's CBR strength. The CBR value of the sub-base soil is crucial to the creation of flexible pavement. CBR strength of the soil can be assessed in both wet and dry conditions [24]. The CBR values depend on the kind of soil and its other characteristics [25]. The CBR test is very time-consuming, tedious, and always carried out on moldy soil samples, which makes it challenging to obtain correct results as well as to put them into practice [26].

The construction of streets requires large amounts of natural resources such as aggregate, and this has negative effects on the environment and future generations [27]. To achieve the theory of sustainability that the Sultanate of Oman seeks, it was necessary to find alternative materials such as waste materials to be exploited instead of natural resources. And, because of the availability of steel slag in tons from the steelmaking process, as well as the problems associated with it, such as the inability to find a place to bury it and the high cost of disposal, it is possible to use steel slag in the process of constructing streets instead of the natural aggregate because it has chemical and mechanical properties like natural aggregate. Also, the materials used in the street layers do have not enough strength to carry the high loads so, the cracks appear, which affects the performance of the street and reduce its lifespan, and because steel slag has high resistance strength, it can be used to improve the street performance. During this research, the replacement of natural aggregate with coarse steel slag will be studied by adding it to the subbase layer, the materials to be used must be tested and evaluated to determine the mechanical properties according to ASSHTO Classification, also the strength of that materials by CBR and Impact aggregate tests.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Due to the presence of many steel factories in the Sultanate of Oman, a sample of steel slag was taken from the Jindal Shadeed factory located in the Wilayat of Liwa. The purpose of this project is to study the ability to use coarse steel slag in road construction and especially the subbase layer instead of natural aggregate. The steel slag is assembled from the factory and stored in the Sohar University laboratory, while the natural aggregate is sourced from Sohar University.

Initially, as a preliminary test is used Grain Sieve Analysis Test and Atterberg Limited Test. The materials used are classified according to the ASSHTO System to determine the usability of these materials as subbases or not. The Standard Procter Test has also been applied to identify the Optimum Moisture Content (OMC) and the Maximum Dry Density (MDD). Afterward, the Impact Aggregate Value Test and the California Bearing Ratio Test were applied to determine the natural aggregate strength before and after the addition of coarse steel slag and to find the appropriate coarse steel slag ratio to supply

the roads with the required strength. The flowchart of the methodology is shown in Figure no.1.

Figure 1: The flowchart of the methodology of the study.

2.1 Grain size distribution

Sieve analysis is a procedure used in civil engineering to evaluate the particle size distribution of granular material by allowing the material to pass through a series of sieves of progressively smaller lattice size and weighing the amount of material returned by each sieve as part of the total mass. The size distribution is often of crucial importance to the way the material works in use. Sieve analysis can be carried out on any type of inorganic or organic granular material including sand, crushed rock, and clay, down to the minimum size depending on the exact method.

The grain size distribution is passed on the percentage retained on each sieve size, which is calculated by:

$$\% \text{ Retained} = \frac{W_{\text{retained}}}{W_{\text{total}}} \times 100\%$$

Important parameters that are obtained from the grain size distribution are the uniformity coefficient (C_u) and the coefficient of gradation (C_c) values, which can be calculated using the diameters D_{10} , D_{30} , and D_{60} , which stand for the percent finer of 10%, 30%, and 60%, respectively. C_u and C_c can be calculated using the formulas below:

$$C_c = D_{30}^2 / (D_{60} \times D_{10})$$

$$C_u = (D_{60} / D_{10})$$

2.2 Atterberg limits test

The Atterberg limits tests pinpoint the moisture levels at which fine-grained clay and silt soils change from solid to semi-solid to plastic to liquid. The liquid limit, plastic limit, and plastic index of soils are still determined using these techniques. The water content at which soil transitions from a liquid to a plastic state is known as the liquid limit (LL), sometimes known as the upper plastic limit. It is the lowest moisture level at which soil flows when a very tiny shear force is applied. The water content at which soil transforms from a plastic to a semisolid condition is known as the plastic limit (PL), sometimes known as the lower plastic limit. The plastic limit test is carried out by manually rolling an ellipsoidal-sized soil mass on a non-porous surface several times. Moreover, The Plasticity Index (PI), a crucial factor in identifying soil types, is created by subtracting the plastic limit from the liquid limit, and can be calculated as follows:

$$PI = LL - PL$$

2.3 Proctor test

A laboratory test to determine the realistic maximum density of a soil sample and the ideal moisture content required to reach that density. The technique encourages the in-situ compaction procedures frequently carried out during the building of earth dams or embankments. After being compacted into moulds of defined volumes and weighed, prepared soil specimens with progressively increased moisture levels are used to determine their unit weights. Up until the optimal moisture level, unit weights will rise with rising moisture contents before falling after that. After accounting for the moisture content, the dry unit weight for each compaction. In order to create a curve that defines the maximum dry density and ideal moisture content, the results are plotted with moisture on the horizontal axis and dry unit weight on the vertical axis. To determine the optimal water content (OMC), for which the value of the dry unit weight is maximal (MDD). The proctor test mainly depends on converting the wet density of soil to dry density with the use of the moisture content (%w) as follows:

$$\text{Dry density} = \frac{\text{Wet density}}{1 + \frac{\%w}{100}}$$

2.4 Aggregate impact value

A relative measurement of an aggregate's resistance to a rapid shock or impact is provided by the impact value test. The soil sample that passes through a 12.5 mm sieve and retracts in a 9.5 mm sieve. The sample is then layered times in a measuring cylinder and tamped down with 25 blows on each layer. the compacted sample is then put in the

cylinder test cup, and 15 blows are applied to the mould using the impact test machine. The sample is placed in a 2.36mm sieve before the weight of the sieve 2.36 mm and the pan is taken. The value of the effect of the aggregate is calculated by determining the ratio of the aggregate passing through the sieve to the total weight of the sample. The value of the effect of the aggregate is calculated by determining the ratio of the aggregate passing through the sieve to the total weight of the sample as follows:

$$\text{The aggregate impact value (AIV)} = \frac{W_2}{W_1} * 100$$

W1: Total weight of sample filling the cylindrical mold of the impact test

W2: Weight of aggregate passing through sieve 2.36 mm after performing the test

2.5 California Bearing Ratio

California Bearing Ratio (CBR) is a test to find the strength of the soil in different road layers to determine the type of soil used in each layer and its ability to withstand the load applied to it by different vehicles. There are specific values for each layer in which the CBR value must not be less than those values. To apply this experiment in the lab, 7.5 kg of the sample to be tested is prepared. After obtaining the optimal amount of water from the Proctor test, the sample is mixed with this water and added to the mould in three layers and compacted. The surface is compacted and levelled and then the mould is placed in the CBR and two surcharges are placed on it weighing 2.5 kg each. The results appear as a curve as a relationship between stress(kg/cm²) on the Y axis and penetration (mm) on the X axis.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Natural Material (0% Steel slag)

The mechanical properties were determined for the soil that will be used as a subbase material. For example, the type of soil was classified by grain sieve analysis test and liquid limit, plastic limit, and plastic index from by Atterberg limit test. By using the AASHTO system the soil was classified, and compaction and drainage were also determined. The Aggregate Impact Value (AIV) is obtained at different percentages of coarse steel slag added to natural coarse aggregate and the values were compared to determine the Optimum steel slag that can resist the sudden load. Then, the optimum moisture content (OMC) and Max Dry Density (MDD) were determined from the Proctor test.

Figure no.2 shows the grain size distribution of the natural material which only contains coarse aggregate. Table 4.1 shows the result of the grain sieve analysis of the coarse aggregate. The percentage of fine is 2.43%, the sand is 12.77%, and the coarse aggregate is 84.8%. According to the AASHTO classification, this sample is granular material. Values of uniformity coefficient (Cu) and Coefficient of curvature (Cc) were found to be 34 and 8.2 respectively. These values mean that the sample is well-graded.

Figure 2: the grain size distribution of the natural material

The proctor test evaluates the soil compaction that will give higher quality and efficiency of soil to be compacted by finding the optimum moisture content (OMC%) that can be added and maximum dry density (MDD). According to figure no.3, the OMC is 4.2% and MDD is 2.17 g/cm³.

Figure 3: The proctor test curve for natural material

The mechanical properties of the natural material are shown in table no.1. The Atterberg limits (liquid and plastic) represent an evaluation of the plastic and liquid behavior of the material. The liquid limit is the water content at which the soil behavior changes from plastic to liquid. The liquid limit of the natural sample was found to be 18.27% which is

less than the specified limit for the subbase layer (25%). The plastic limit is considered the average water content which was found to be 14.71%, and the plastic index, which is the difference between the two values, was found to be 3.56, which is less than the limit of the subbase layer (6%).

Regarding the impact value of the aggregate, the value shows the resistance to shock, in which the aggregate is ensured to be strong enough for pavement construction and that it can effectively withstand the load. The impact value for the natural aggregate was found to be 12.872%, which is less than 20%. Consequently, the sample is considered acceptable for the subbase layer.

Table I: The mechanical properties of the natural material

Test	Result	Standard Values
Liquid limit	18.27%	25% Max
Plastic limit	14.71%	-
Plastic index	3.56	6 Max
Optimum moisture content (OMC)	4.2%	-
Maximum dry density	2.17 g/m ³	-
Impact value	12.872%	10–20%

3.2 Evaluation of coarse steel slag mixtures:

3.2.1 Evaluation Based on Sieve Distribution Analysis and Atterberg Limits:

Through the results that appear in figures 4, 5, 6, and 7 to evaluate coarse aggregate modified by coarse steel slag, it is clear that the modified material is within standard limits of subbase materials for highway (class A) and secondary road (class B). The group index (GI) is 0 at 0%, 5%, and 10% of steel slag, which indicates the excellent ability of this material for drainage and compaction system in the subbase layer. As a result, the modified coarse aggregate is excellent in the soil classification tests for the subbase.

Figure 4: Subbase Class A evaluation for the natural aggregate sample.

Figure 5: Subbase Class A evaluation for the modified aggregate sample.

Figure 6: Subbase Class B evaluation for the natural aggregate sample.

Figure 7: Subbase Class B evaluation for the modified aggregate sample.

3.2.2 Evaluation Based on Aggregate Impact Value (AIV):

The aggregate Impact value test was applied to determine the ability of natural aggregate modified by coarse steel slag to resist the sudden impact of the vehicles on the subbase layer. The result was obtained as it appears in Figure no. 8. The AIV is 12.8%, 14.7%, 15.4%, 15.6%, 13.1%, and 13.3% respectively with increasing amounts of coarse steel slag. All values are less than 30%, so according to the standard these materials can be used for the subbase layer, but the best mix is at 20% coarse steel slag.

The proportions of the sample were evaluated after adding a certain percentage of steel slag to it. As shown in Table no.2, the results show that the use of steel slag does not affect the natural aggregate used in the subbase layer to resist sudden loads because all values are still much less than the Max Aggregate Impact Value, which should not be less than 30% in the subbase layer. The minimum AIV is at 20% of SS.

Figure 8: Aggregate impact value results for steel slag mixtures

Table II: Aggregate impact value results for steel slag mixtures

Natural coarse aggregate %	Coarse steel slag %	AIV%	Subbase layer
100.000	0	12.872	✓
95.000	5	14.700	✓
90.000	10	15.400	✓
85.000	15	15.600	✓
80.000	20	13.094	✓
75.000	2	13.300	✓

3.2.3 Evaluation Based on California Bearing Ratio (CBR):

The California Bearing Ratio (CBR) was obtained at 10, 30, and 65 blows and compared the values at all samples that are with different amounts of coarse steel slag. Moreover, the samples were evaluated at different percentages of steel slag added to determine the optimum steel slag that can be used with natural coarse aggregate in the subbase materials. To evaluate according to CBR, the materials of subbase must have a value of

CBR not less than 30%. As table no. 3 appears the modified aggregate of 10% to 20% can be used in the subbase layer. Figures 9, 10, and 11 show the values of CBR for 10 blows, 30 blows, and 65 blows respectively. Figure 9 illustrated that the value of CBR of natural coarse aggregate at 10 blows less than 30% means that this material cannot be used at less compaction, but the value of CBR increases gradually after adding 10% of SS until it reaches the highest value when adding 19% of SS. At 30 and 65 blows (Figures 10 and 11) the values of CBR also rise after increasing the amount of SS to 19%. It is clear from the figures that after increasing the percentage of steel slag to more than 19%, the CBR values went down but they are still greater than 30%. The highest values of CBR are at 19% of SS. Hence, the optimum percent of steel slag that gives the highest CBR value is 19%.

Table III: CBR values of Steel slag mixtures at different blows

No of blows	Percentage of steel slag (SS%)							
	0%	5%	10%	15%	17%	19%	20%	25%
10	17.991	16.546	35.039	55.479	65.766	79.701	56.612	37.752
30	66.775	35.287	56.716	75.448	142.498	156.758	91.741	113.149
65	82.049	78.203	123.952	120.164	158.456	162.386	88.201	122.828

Figure 9: CBR values at 10 blows

Figure 10: CBR values at 30 blows

Figure 11: CBR values at 65 blows

4. CONCLUSION

The rise in industrial activities has caused a notable rise in the production of industrial waste. Among this waste, steel slag is a major contributor to the negative environmental impact. Steel slag is typically discarded in landfills, leading to environmental contamination. This research aimed to explore the feasibility of using coarse steel slag as a component in road subbase material. Implementing this approach, would support the development of eco-friendly pavements, help conserve natural resources, and enhance the durability and strength of the pavement system.

Various laboratory tests were conducted to obtain the soil classification tests as Grain Sieve Analysis and Atterberg limit test, also California Bearing Ratio (CBR) and Aggregate Impact Value (AIV) tests to determine the strength of this material. The results were compared at different percentages of steel slag to determine the optimum steel slag that gives a greater ability to resist sudden loads and a higher value of CBR. The results showed that the addition of 19% of steel slag to the natural aggregate will give the subbase layer a high ability to resist loads, which improves the performance and increases the life period of the streets. Moreover, Sustainability in pavement constructions was achieved sustainability by minimizing natural aggregate depletion and using steel slag as an alternative material in the subbase layer.

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